

MEDIATION AS AN ADDITIONAL TYPE OF SPEECH ACTIVITY

Shukhratzoda Sevarakhon Dilshod kizi,
master's degree student
Uzbekistan State World Languages University
Normuratova Valentina Ivanovna, s
upervisor
Uzbekistan State World Languages University

***Abstract:** This work devoted to the study of the effectiveness of mediation as an additional type of speech activity. The work was based on Companion Volume CEFR 2018. The participants were analyzed according to the mediation of different degrees of knowledge ranging from A1 to C2. In the literature review were cited examples of the work of different scientists. This study is to provide a more in-depth explanation of the application mediation in speech activity and effort to improve learners' reading skills.*

***Key terms:** mediation, mediator, speech, speech activity.*

Introduction

Speech is an integral part of human social life, a necessary condition for the existence of all mankind, is a necessary condition for human cognitive activity. Through speech a person learns, acquires knowledge and transmits it. Speech is a means of meeting a person's personal needs for communication. No human being on earth can live without communication with other people: he must advise, share his thoughts, experiences, empathize, seek understanding, etc.

In speech activity, a person produces and perceives information transformed into a text. There are four types of speech activity. Two of which are involved in text production (information transfer) - speaking and writing; and another two are involved in the perception of the text, the information embedded in it - listening and reading.

Mediation is very actual theme nowadays in Uzbekistan, because nobody researched it before. Mediation is the result of intermediation, a key aspect of

communication that arises when we take into account the needs of others and adjust our own expression accordingly. When we mediate, we think not only about what to say, but also about how to say it. To put it in simple terms Mediation is when understanding develops while you are trying to explain something specific to someone.

In general, mediation involves actions that:

- Helping people understand each other.
- Make things more understandable
- Make connections between ideas and information
- Support a "discussion of things" to come to new conclusions.

Therefore, updated CEFR (2018) recommendations suggested four main dimensions of English language competence: reception, production, interaction, and mediation. The last dimension is focused on adapting the information, collaborating, explaining, synthesizing texts and ideas, managing successful interaction. The mediation skill is not completely new, but it has been transformed into a more extended and more interactive way of language, cultural, and social competence acquisition. So, this dimension can complement rather than replace the course goals. Mediation is a crucial skill that combines language competence and “soft” skills for meaningful information communication (Lavrysh, 2016).

Mediation has recently become a hot topic of discussion in language learning because the concept has been significantly updated in the CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages). So it's important to note that mediation is not something that can be added to the four skills. Rather, it is an aspect of how we use the four skills and often combine them. This study is to provide a more in-depth explanation of the application mediation in speech activity and effort to improve learners' reading skills.

Literature review

Researcher found some quotes related to mediation, which she would like to share.

Mediation allows parties to have a face-to-face discussion/conversation about their issues. This allows them to be directly involved in resolving the issues rather than having a third party decide on the outcome (Kovach, 2010). Mediation gives both the parties the opportunity not only to talk through all the issues involved in the dispute but also how they may influence the process and the outcome of the mediation. These issues do not necessarily always have legal meaning but often involve emotional damage or personal offense (Kovach, 2010). Face-to-face discussion also allows the parties to express their expectations that are not monetarily driven (Kovach, 2003). For example, some disputes involve one party simply wanting an apology from the other party. However this can often lead to problems as an apology is often viewed as an admission of guilt (Robbennolt & Sternlight, 2012). But in mediation, parties are able to discuss all consequences of such apologies even if the apology causes certain hardships related to the confidentiality of the mediation.

Another advantage of mediation is the ability for the parties to look at their past, current, and future relationships (Goodman, 2005). These relationships can be strictly business oriented, contract agreement oriented, or family/parentally oriented. The mediator often asks the parties about their wants, interests and willingness to continue the relationship that they currently have (Frenkel & Stark, 2008).

Meditators have a very important and delicate position in the mediation. They must simultaneously control the progression of the mediation, while also giving the parties control over the agreements, decisions and discussions between the parties. The parties participating in the mediation can be the individuals in conflict, (such as the couple in a divorce mediation) the lawyers representing the individuals, or even the parties with their lawyers (Kovach, 2010). Each of these

circumstances requires a different approach, according to the mediation's specific needs. This involves a great deal of flexibility, on the mediator's role, in creating the approach that is necessary for the specific moment within each mediation. Since mediations are centered on conversation and communication between the parties facilitated by the mediator, the mediator must have very adaptive language skills.

There are two main types of sessions that occur within mediation. The first is the "joint session" which includes the mediator meeting concurrently with all the individuals from both parties to discuss the issues at hand (Kovach, 2010). This can be very productive in understanding the facts, the issues, and how the other party sees the same situation, but can get out of control because of the emotions and many pre-existing biases that accompany many conflicts. The other type of session is called a "caucus" in which one party, or even just one individual, meets with the mediator at a time (Kovach, 2010). The mediator meets individually with both parties in order to give both parties equal opportunities to speak privately with the mediator and maintain the rules of neutrality and impartiality. This can be used to receive extra information from the party or simply to settle emotions between the parties and remove the tension of the parties being face to face (Frenkel & Stark, 2008). Due to the large variation in the many areas of mediation, including character of the dispute, who the participants are, and past relationship dynamics between the parties, mediators may use these two different types of sessions to adapt to the specific mediation dynamics. (Gmurzynska & Morek, 2014). Mediation tends to consist mostly of joint sessions if communication between the parties (with help of the mediator) flows smoothly (Gmurzynska & Morek, 2014). On the other hand, mediation may consist mostly of caucuses if there are many obstacles in communication and the exchange of information between the parties (Gmurzynska & Morek, 2014). Mediators may also organize individual sessions

with each side to address specific issues such as emotional barriers, lack of communication, withholding an offer, etc.

The mediator then uses the different steps of mediation (i.e., joint sessions, caucus, discussion with lawyers, agreement points/commonalities) to help the parties to have a productive conversation about resolving the issues between them (Goodman, 2005). The mediator sometimes acts as a medium of communication between the two parties. If there are negative attitudes, emotions and other barriers between the parties that are not allowing them to hold a productive conversation, the mediator will meet with the parties separately and relay information from one party to the other (Fisher & Brown, 1988). This physical separation of parties is sometimes necessary, and the party's hearing propositions and negotiation points from the third party neutral can be perceived as less biased, less manipulative, and fairer. The parties may be more agreeable and reasonable, when hearing information from the mediator, who is neutral in the conflict, instead of hearing it from the other party (Robbennolt & Sternlight, 2012). In this way the mediator serves as a translator between the parties, rewording, restating, or even summarizing information between the parties in order to help them communicate efficiently. The mediator gives the parties a medium through which to ease communication between the sides.

Methodology

The study utilized qualitative research method also used library research, which included several activities, collecting information and data from various sources such as "reference books, previous results of similar research, articles, notes and journals related to book, results of previous similar research, articles, notes and journals related to the problem at hand" (Sari, 2020). Further, this research was conducted by identifying and seeking information from relevant data, analyzing the findings, and then developing and presenting ideas (Rasmuson). This study reviewed the literature related to the implementation of mediation and

specifically how mediators use language to adapt to different mediation situations and facilitate the mediation process according to "Companion Volume - CEFR (2018). The development and validation of mediation scales is described in "Developing Illustrative Descriptors of Mediation Aspects for CEFR" (North and Piccardo 2016). The goal was to provide CEFR descriptors for the broader view of mediation presented in "Education, Mobility, and Otherness - Mediation Functions of Schools" (Coste and Cavalli 2015).

Results

In mediation, the user/learner acts as a social agent who creates bridges and helps build or convey meaning, Sometimes within the same language, sometimes between modalities (e.g., from spoken to written or vice versa, in cross-modal communication), and sometimes from one language to another (cross-linguistic mediation). On the site. The focus is on the role of language in such processes as creating space and conditions for communication and/or learning, collaborating to create new meaning, encouraging others to create or understand new meaning and communicating new information in an appropriate form (CEFR, 2018). The participants were analyzed according to the mediation of different degrees of knowledge ranging from A1 to C2. You can see the results of the analysis below in Table.

Grade	General mediation
A1	Can use simple words/signs and non-verbal signals to show interest in an idea. Can convey simple, predictable information of immediate interest given in short, simple signs and notices, posters and programs.
A2	Can play a supportive role in interaction, provided other participants speak/sign slowly and that one or more of the participants helps them to contribute and to express their suggestions. Can use simple words/signs to ask someone to explain something. Can recognize when difficulties occur and indicate in simple language the apparent nature of a problem.

B1	Can collaborate with people from other backgrounds, showing interest and empathy by asking and answering simple questions, formulating and responding to suggestions, asking whether people agree, and proposing alternative approaches.
B2	Can establish a supportive environment for sharing ideas and facilitate discussion of delicate issues, showing appreciation of different perspectives, encouraging people to explore issues and adjusting sensitively the way they express things.
C1	Can act effectively as a mediator, helping to maintain positive interaction by interpreting different perspectives, managing ambiguity, anticipating misunderstandings and intervening diplomatically in order to redirect the conversation.
C2	Can mediate effectively and naturally, taking on different roles according to the needs of the people and situation involved, identifying nuances and undercurrents and guiding a sensitive or delicate discussion.

Conclusion

Taking everything into consideration, there are many different aspects of mediation, but all share certain characteristics. For example, in mediation one is less concerned with one's own needs, ideas or expression than with those of the party or parties for whom one is mediating. A person who engages in mediation activity needs to have a well-developed emotional intelligence, or an openness to develop it, in order to have sufficient empathy for the viewpoints and emotional states of other participants in the communicative situation. The term "mediation" is also used to describe a social and cultural process of creating conditions for communication and co-operation, facing and hopefully defusing any delicate

situations and tensions that may arise. Cross-linguistic and cross-modal mediation, in particular, inevitably involve social and cultural competence as well as plurilingual competence. This emphasizes the fact that one cannot in practice completely separate one type of mediation from another. In adapting descriptors to their context, therefore, users should feel free to mix and match categories to suit their own perspective.

The CEFR now gives us detailed descriptors of what learners "can do" in a range of mediation activities at levels A1-C2. These descriptors have been published in the CEFR Companion Volume (2018). It is important to note here that the CEFR does not break things down into four skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Instead, it describes four "modes" to better reflect how communication happens in real life:

- Reception: understanding while listening and reading
- Production: formulating something new to say or write
- Interaction: engaging in a conversation or written exchange
- Mediation: tailoring the message to the recipient.

References

- Goodman, A. H. (2005). *Basic Skills for the New Mediator*. Rockville, MD: Solomon Publications.
- Gmurzynska, E., & Morek, R. (2014). *Mediacje: teoria I praktyka*. Warsaw, PL: Wolters Kluwer.
- Fisher, R., & Brown, S. (1988). *Getting Together*. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Frenkel, D.N., and Stark, J.H. (2008). *The Practice of Mediation*. New York: Aspen Publishers.
- Kovach, K.K., (2003). *Mediation in a Nutshell*. St. Paul, MN: West.

Kovach, K. K. (2010). Mediation: Principles and Practice. St.Paul: West Group.

Lavrysh, Y. 2016. Peer and self-assessment at ESP classes: case study. In: Advanced education, vol. 6, pp. 60-68. ISSN 2410-8286.

Robbennolt, J.K., and Sternlight, J.R. (2012). Psychology for Lawyers: Understanding the human factors in negotiation, litigation, and decision making. Chicago, Il: ABA Publishing.